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Paving the way for more accurate earth system modelling in Malaysia

T A S T M Suhari¹, Eranga M Wimalasiri*^{1,2} and Ebrahim Jahanshiri¹

¹Crops for the Future UK, NIAB, 93 Lawrence Weaver Road, Cambridge, England, UK

²Department of Export Agriculture, Faculty of Agricultural Sciences, Sabaragamuwa University of Sri Lanka, Belihuloya, 70140, Sri Lanka

*Corresponding author: eranga.wimalasiri@cropsforthefutureuk.org

Abstract. Variations in soil structural and physiochemical properties can impact earth system models related to climate change. However, in most of the countries including Malaysia, soil data are available as low resolution and semi-detailed soil series maps, which hinder their applicability. Therefore, the objective of this study was to develop a framework to compare the conventional soil mapping with digital soil databases and to determine the accuracy of digital soil mapping. Kedah province located in the northern region of Peninsular Malaysia was selected as the study area. Observed soil (Cation exchange capacity – CEC, pH, organic matter as chemical and clay, sand and silt content as physical properties) data published by the Department of Agriculture, Malaysia was compared with SoilGrid (soilgrid.org) dataset. The depths of observed data were harmonised to international standard soil depths as; 0-5, 5-15, 15-30, 30-60, 60-100, and 100-200 cm using the equal quadratic spline approach. Global data were compared with harmonised 16 selected soil series data in Malaysia. Observed soil chemical properties (CEC, pH, and organic carbon) were within the range of SoilGrids data which allows the selected chemical properties to be used where observed data are limited or not available. In contrast, most of the soil physical properties from SoilGrids were not accurate when compared with the observed data. The developed framework in this study can be used to strengthen the accuracy of the available soil data in Earth system models, particularly those that are related to organic carbon and soil structural properties.

Keywords : Conventional soil mapping, SoilGrids, soil harmonization, spline tools

1. Introduction

Soil information plays a pivotal role in climate change studies, particularly those that are related to soil carbon storage [1] microbiome [2], geomorphological process and ecosystem health [3] and agricultural land use and land degradation [4] [5]. In Malaysia close to 500 soil series were identified and mapped as an extensive variety of soils of mountainous, hilly, rolling, undulating, level and swampy terrain landscapes are [6]. The association of mapping units is very helpful in determining general soil types across the country and for regional and national planning activities. However, such data are rarely useful for detailed analysis such as a change in carbon stocks and other climate change related studies.

The digital soil mapping technique for mapping of soil properties also has not yet been implemented in Malaysia. A major reason for this is that soil profile data are rarely made available publicly and the availability of such data depends solely on conventional survey methods for specific purposes which are

often very limited in Malaysia. Per-property soil maps are available at a global scale, alas with limited detail and they are already being used for studies in Malaysia [7].

A harmonised data of soil property profiles in Malaysia can pave the way for more accurate mapping of important soil properties such as soil organic carbon and soil carbon stock and carbon pool that is directly related to the climate change studies [8] [9]. Therefore, it is crucial to compare data that are traditionally provided based on conventional soil series maps and those that are available globally through digital soil mapping techniques. Therefore, the objective of this study was to develop a framework to compare the conventional soil mapping with digital soil databases and to determine the accuracy of digital soil mapping which will lead to accurate earth system modelling in Malaysia.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area

Kedah province which is located in the northern region of Peninsular Malaysia was selected as the study area. The province covers approximately 10,430 km² area. The area has a tropical climate with generally flat terrain (elevation 60 m above sea level). The land use map of Kedah is shown in Figure 1. Paddy is the major crop while different types of land use systems that include rubber, oil palm and some fruit crops such as pineapple are observed in the area. A major part of the area is covered by Lowland Forest.

Figure 1. Land Use Map of Kedah

2.2. Data

To cover both physical and chemical soil properties, pH, clay (%), sand (%) and silt content (%), organic carbon (%), and cation exchange capacity (cmol/kg) were selected. The semi detailed soil map developed by the Department of Agriculture, Malaysia was used as observed data. The Kedah province consists of 16 soil series as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Available soil series and the respective major soil groups in the study region

No	Soil ID	Mapping Unit Reference	Soil Series	Major Soil Group
1	A	37	Beriah-Tanah Liat Organan & Muck	Marine Alluvial Soil
2	B	26	Durian-Melaka-Tavy	Sedentary Soil
3	C	18	Holyrood-Lunas	Riverine Alluvial Soil
4	D	15	Hutan-Semberin	Riverine Alluvial Soil
5	E	2	Keranji	Marine Alluvial Soil
6	F	37	Langkawi	Limestone Material
7	G	28	Muncung-Serdang	Sedentary Soil
8	H	31	Rengan-Jerangau	Sedentary Soil
9	I	1	Rudua-Rusila	Marine Alluvial Soil
10	J	3	Sedu-Parit Botak-Linau	Marine Alluvial Soil
11	K	30	Serdang-Bungor-Muncung'	Sedentary Soil
12	L	16	Sogomana-Sitiawan-Manik	Riverine Alluvial Soil
13	M	11	Telemung-Akob-Lanar Tempatan	Riverine Alluvial Soil
14	N	27	Muncung-Seremban	Sedentary Soil
15	O	47	Rengam-Bukit Temiang	Sedentary Soil
16	P	25	Gajah Mati-Muncung-Melaka	Reworked Soil

Note: Soil ID was given by authors for easy identification while Soil Mapping Unit refers to the code of identification given by the Department of Agriculture, Malaysia.

Global soil data were retrieved from SoilGrids (soilgrid.org) dataset which is available at 250 m resolution [10]. Around 150,000 profile data points from the World Soil Information Service (WoSIS) and other sources were used to develop Soil Grids database. The SoilGrids database has been used in various earth systems and agricultural related applications in different geographical scales [7] [11] [12].

2.3. Harmonization of attributes and mapping

Soil attribute varies continuously with depth in a soil profile which hinders proper comparison and application [13]. Also, the data in semi-detailed soil maps are available for different depths that are vary among locations. Therefore, soil properties were harmonised using the equal quadratic spline approach into international standard soil depths as; 0-5, 5-15, 15-30, 30-60, 60-100, and 100-200 cm. The SplineTool v2 (available at: <http://www.asris.csiro.au>) was used for harmonisation.

2.4. Data analysis

Global soil data from SoilGrids were compared with 16 selected soil series (mapping units) in the Kedah province (Table 1). The data of 0-30 cm depth were compared and other data were omitted due to lack of information for all the locations. The averages of the standard depth intervals (0-30 cm) were obtained using the integration method.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Mapping the smoothing spline soil depth function

Three standardised datasets were created the equal-area spline depth function; the actual data, the spline curve and the standardised depth data. The actual data, for example, soil organic carbon content are real observations based on soil horizon that were determined by the surveyors based on the profile

morphological features. The best fitted equal area spline was derived and used in the harmonisation of depths for each soil property. The lambda (λ) value of 0.1 reported the best fitted splines on test data.

Estimates of the quality of the predictions were obtained by the calculation of Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) values which measure the difference between the true and fitted function. Figure 2 shows a fitted spline of sand content (%) as an example. Please note that this spline interpolation has been done for all tested soil properties in each location.

Figure 2. Fitted spline of sand content (%) for different soil depths. The original sampled soil profiles are in blue rectangles, the predicted six standard depths in purple rectangles and the fitted spline with 1 cm interval is in red line.

3.2. Comparison between conventional and digital soil mapping approaches

Comparison of observed and global soil data of selected properties is shown in Figures 3 and 4. Observed soil chemical properties (CEC, pH and organic carbon) were within the range of SoilGrids data which allows selected chemical properties to be used where observed data are limited or not available. Soil pH data obtained from SoilGrids were used in crop suitability assessment in Malaysia and resulted in a higher (89%) median accuracy of estimation [11].

In contrast to chemical properties, most of the data points of observed soil physical properties (sand, silt and clay content) were beyond the global soil data which hinders their applicability in gap filling of observed data. However, these uncertainties may also be associated with measurement errors during the original soil survey and prediction errors during the data integration.

Having both dataset with different periods of data acquisition could also give dissimilarities in both values in soil chemical and physical characteristics as in Figure 3. The soil condition could be changed due to several factors such as urbanization, land degradation, climate change, and natural disaster, and many more.

Figure 3. Comparison between observed (conventional) and predicted (global) data for 6 soil pH (a); cation exchange capacity (b); organic carbon (c); clay (d); silt (e); sand (f)

Figure 4. Comparison of conventional and digital soil mapping data for Kedah, Malaysia

When consider soil texture, the SoilGrids data showed overestimation compared to silt and clay on which a fairly good estimation was reported for them (Figure 4). In chemical properties, soil pH values had the best relationship between both datasets (Figure 4). Previous comparisons of soil organic carbon

between regional databases and SoilGrids showed that SoilGrids was the closest to the field measurements in several geographic scales [14]. The uncertainties and errors could be due to measurement errors, prediction during the original soil survey or data integration.

Although SoilGrids data provide worldwide soil information, the samples of observations for some areas are lacking particularly for Malaysia. Wider selection of soil observations and more profile observations will increase the quality assessment and improve the consistency and standardisation across the different points datasets would give better accuracies for global available dataset in the future with no doubt [15].

3.3. Applicability of the work and future work

Although the statistical analysis determined that both data have significant differences, it shows that both conventional soil mapping and digital soil mapping have the capability in providing a source of soil information for environmental research such as monitoring the soil changes and earth systems and environmental modelling. Conventional soil mapping has the potential in generating detailed soil information on a regional scale. Figure 5 shows the schematic process flow chart developed in this study.

However, this study should be extended and more work is needed in larger geographical scales including the additional datasets and covariates that would be necessary to test these possibilities systematically.

Figure 5. Process flow chart of the study

4. Conclusions

Conventional and digital soil mapping was compared in this study with the aim of developing a framework that assists in earth systems modelling in Malaysia. The comparison of the soil maps generally showed a significant difference for soil physical properties whereas no significant difference was reported for soil pH, a chemical property. Conventional soil data which were derived from observations have to be used in Earth Systems modelling and need to be integrated with digital soil maps such as SoilGrids. The developed framework in this study can be used to strengthen the accuracy of the available soil data in Earth system models related to climate change.

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